

Modern Trends and Practices in E-Marketing

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OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 1

Month:

Year: 2019

P-ISSN: 2320-4168

E-ISSN: 2582-0729

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Tamilselvan, S.

“Modern Trends
and Practices in

E-Marketing.” *Shanlax
International Journal of
Commerce*, vol. 7,
no. S1, 2019,
pp. 231–34.

DOI:

[https://doi.org/10.5281/
zenodo.3451706](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3451706)

Abstract

With the unprecedented growth technology in the global world, the internet plays a paramount role in all major areas of our life and industries. Within few clicks we can explore ample information which helps will help in conceptualizing many tasks in nanoseconds and realizing the power of internet, marketing is not far back to use it as a driving channel to lead the global territory. E-marketing also known as digital marketing comprises the usage of virtual digital space with a scope of interaction, this digital space is used by the marketer to develop and sell the products and services. This internet-based marketing played a vital role to uplift the different economic sectors with special emphasis on marketing. Considering this is a cost-effective, fast, and flexible way to reach the audience of global diasporas-marketing bring sustainable business gains. However-marketing has its own sets of limitations that include more of tech touch instead of personnel touch, ensuring the safety and security with the aspect of privacy infringement. The paper starts with a concept, how different e-marketing is from traditional marketing, and different strategies of e-marketing the advantages, limitations, its future and conclusion.

Keywords: cost, global, internet, marketing, online.

Introduction

Over the years, marketing and its ways to reach the global world is transformed, and the key role in this transformation has been played on the internet. The easy availability of internet has led to the progressive and interconnected environment, and the phenomenal increase of the internet has resulted in the declining trends if traditional media which primary covers the usage of television, banners, radio, print media, and large hooding. Marketing in this closely connected conditions and using this connectivity to market the stocks and services is e-marketing. E-marketing includes a wide spectrum of strategies and methods, but the basic fundamental of successful e-marketing is a user-friendly and well-designed approach to these strategies. E-marketing includes the management of the consumer’s real-time online viability of the product, from first online experience through marketing to delivery of the product and the individual service beyond delivery. One of the major benefits of electronic marketing is the underlying messages are not restricted by geography or time.

Concept

E-marketing referred as online marketing, or internet marketing is a selling technique where we are channelizing the marketing and promotion online with the aid of internet that further incorporations online advertising, using emails and social networking for notice, here every aspect is marketed and promoted online and is totally connected to distribution and sales. With major center on global reach E-marketing comprises public relations, information management, and consumer service with immediacy impact where the answer from the set of customers can be obtained in an immediate real-time, e-marketing improves a two way communication between the companies and the customer with cost minimization and speeding up the buying cycle with planning quick points for business development. E-marketing helps to understand and target the niche market by knowing their requirements well and delivering the same with lesser time and cost.

How Different from Traditional Marketing

- If we compare the methods of online marketing with conventional traditional marketing practices, then there are ample areas and opportunities where online marketing is competent and has its advantages.
- Unlike traditional marketing, where we have to wait for the stipulated time frame to find out the response from the customers, online marketing is real-time.
- Since we can get the response of the customers in real-time, it is easier to track if a special campaign is working for the product or not and based on the feedback marketer can make the appropriate changes in the promotional campaign, in traditional marketing, this compliance is not possible.
- In traditional marketing, it is hard for small retailers to compete with the big competitors in the market owing to the cost involved and strategy making expertise whereas in case of online marketing, through the crisp website you can reach your target audience with wider range with more reliable service assurance.
- Cost involvement is another point which produces a lot of difference between the conventional selling techniques over online shopping; a business house can create its digital marketing plan with very little cost and succeed over costly advertising methods such as print media, radio coverage, television, and magazines.
- With electronic shopping, marketer can create options to stimulate their target users to take positive appropriate action, visit the special website, to learn about their stocks and its leaders and various services, by this tool customers can express their viewpoint about the product, their choice of getting the stock and even feedback, which is also visible in the website thus by this way the marketer gets an efficient opportunity to join with the consumers, which is usually diluted in case of traditional mode of markets.
- Online marketing has the potential to create a ripple and viral effect in promotion over traditional mode marketing, for instance using social media networking website, email and social media channels publishes the content of the information to be shared incredibly quickly.

Different Methods of E-Marketing

E-marketing or online shopping can be promoted and executed by the following techniques and methods

Online Advertising: This is the most well-known technique which is developed under e-marketing, where the marketer uses practical space to communicate and promote the marketing content on exclusively designed web pages to bring the attention of the internet users, here the major

objective is to increase brand awareness and propagate sales. This method involves promotional messages on the computer screen, it is more like a TV commercial, but online attacks are more creative.

Mobile Marketing: Increasing innovations in smart phones created an opportunity for consumers to use and connect with online possibilities of publicity. Advancement of technology in mobile phones raises the avenues for mobile marketing in a random fashion. The trend of mobile marketing has been welcomed by restaurants and movie theaters and with each passing year banks and financial institutions also using this process of marketing.

E-mail marketing: This mode of online marketing is considered one of the most effective way of e-marketing where emails are being used for sending promotional messages to internet users. The major benefit of this method is lower costs and a broader reach, but this method has its limitations as the online consumer can easily ignore the received advertisement content or the consumer can put these emails in a spam folder.

Video Marketing: In this method of e-marketing, video is added to the website to increase the website traffic at a higher rate. In this mode, it is necessary that the relevant information needs to be conveyed to the target public thus the video needs to be designed in a manner where it will be able to know and explain the needs of the customer else the whole initiative will be futile.

Social media marketing: This technique creates brand recognition and boost the product by using social networking sites by creating unique content that draws the attention of the social networking users, and they share it with their set of friends.

Corporate Video: This process comprises the usage of online interactive video and thus more successful in conveying the desired message to the target public and have the feature of easy sharing and cost-effective in terms of creation and can be accessed across the globe.

Advantages of E-Marketing

Over the years, e-marketing became the preferred way of conducting and promoting the business to cut expenses and increase the business profitability, which is unlike in the case of traditional marketing methods which emphasize on mass marketing. Electronic marketing method can be designed in such a manner to reach target set of customers or niche customers having specific expectation and preference for the products or services apparently based on the specific digital marketing campaign promotion, apart from the expenses cost and its reach another factor which makes e-marketing more vibrant is its flexibility and its quality adherence , Online media is instant and round the clock available for usage, for example, a marketing promotion via a website is accessible 24/7, the messages keep on reinforced and any kind of changes in the content can be updated in real-time with no geographical barriers. E-marketing ensures better quality check in terms of measurability and practice tracks. In traditional marketing techniques since there is very limited scope for the advertiser to connect with customers unlike in e-marketing engagement with a target customer in real-time is the key which in turn help the advertiser to know the customers and their needs well.

Limitations of E-Marketing

One of the biggest limitations of e-marketing is its reach, and functioning is limited by the ability of the consumer to access and use Internet services. Though over the years the importance and usage of Internet increases manifold in the community of developed and modern world still substantial strata of consumers are unable to make use of the internet or very limited access to it, especially in the rural areas. Security and privacy are different concern area in e-marketing with an equal danger of being copied by the opponent as the level of competition are quiet huge in

e-marketing credit goes to lower cost in the creation and vast reach. The content and the message should be very clear in online advertising campaigns else it may lose the underlying stock with negative feedback from the consumers which may hinder not only the marketing promotion but also damage the overall brand value.

Future of E-Marketing

The future of e-marketing is promising, with the length and power of social networking places, the virtual field of marketing is lucrative in terms of moment and option creation for global public and giving service in customer doorstep in a cost-effective manner, though the different methods of online marketing is then covered, the improvement of technology make the future of online marketing very hopeful with the coming future trends in place

- Mechanism of Cost per click – Considering the major portion of online marketing promotion put towards the usage of digital technology, the scalability, and effectiveness of advertisement is more profound in this method. Though there is a risk that the market will become overburdened; however, with the trend of inflation, this method is profitable.
- Model of Cost per action buying –This digital advertising technique is upcoming and is the key focus area for online advertisers as 50% of the promotional budget is associated for these trends owing to the potential of reaching the maximum amount of customers independent of location
- Verticalisation is going to be an active and well-strategized e-marketing trend where marketers target their specific audience. The application area in this technique is niche consumers, and for them, the marketers come out with the strategy to deliver the specific message to its set following.
- With an improvement in the options of online display, its combination with search marketing is going to be a popular trend. Through this mode of e-marketing, the users who are entering the website become a customer, and considering the cost optimization with this process, the return of expense for the marketer is better and promising.

Conclusion

The Internet has emerged as a revolution in the overall aspect of our life, starting from a broader economy to marketing. This study reveals the concept of e-marketing with current strategies and its superiority over traditional marketing with set of advantages covers wide coverage of global population, reaching the point set of consumers and to get respective feedback from them about the result thus creating greater opportunity to engage with them with quick and efficient results in optimal cost and scalable result. With each passing day as the Internet is evolving, latest technologies and different marketing tactics will emerge in the electronic platform of marketing and redefine how different and new products and services will be marketed uniquely in the coming days.

References

1. <http://www.google.co.in/url?sa=t&source=web&rct=j&url=http://www.iosrjournals.org/>
2. <http://www.google.co.in/url?st&source=weeb&url=http://www.failteireland.ie/>